

Paper 8

A STUDY ON CUSTOMERS OPINION ON BANKING PRODUCTS AND SERVICES WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO SELECTED BRANCHES OF KASARAGODU DISTRICT COOPERATIVE BANK

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Abstract

Banking sector is the service industry which has shown a dramatic growth and development consistently for the last several decades. Banking industry of any country is highly instrumental in determining the magnitude of the developments of the industry and citizens of that country. India's banking sector has been characterized by the strong presence of public sector, private sector, cooperative and foreign banks. Cooperative banks that include the primary cooperatives, district cooperative banks and the state cooperative banks cater to the needs of the common man especially of the people working in the primary sector to a great extent. The district cooperative banks in Kerala are grown-up to a higher level that now they offer the services and facilities that are as competent as the one offered by any other well established commercial bank. This study has made an attempt to evaluate the opinion of the customers towards the products, services and facilities offered by the selected six branches of the Kasaragodu district cooperative bank. Twenty respondents were chosen from each of these banks taking the sample size of the study to 120. The information was collected on factors such as Service capabilities, Customer services, ATM services, Employees, Paperless banking, Service quality and Product features. Statistical tools such as Kruskal Wallis Test and Mann-Whitney, Weighted average and Percentage analysis, were used to analyze the data collected.

Keywords: service industry, banking sector, district cooperative banks, customer services

1.Introduction to the research problem

India's banking industry is portrayed by the well-built existence of public and private sectors, cooperative and foreign banks. Cooperative banks accommodate to the needs of the common man especially of the people engaged in agriculture or small business. The district cooperative banks in Kerala play a substantial role in satisfying the banking needs of the people, especially the rural and sub-urban areas. The products, services and other facilities offered by the district cooperative banks are as competent as that of a well established commercial bank. Therefore, it is very important for the bank to know the level of satisfaction of its customers about the products, services or the facilities provided to the customers. The most comprehensive definition of customer satisfaction has been offered by Kotler and Keller who define satisfaction as

“person’s feeling of pleasure or disappointment which resulted from comparing a product’s perceived performance or outcome against his/ her expectations” (Kotler and Keller, 2006) .This study has made an attempt to evaluate the opinion of the customers towards the products, services and facilities offered by the selected six branches of the Kasaragodu district cooperative bank.

2.Review of literature

M. Selvam (2005) in his article entitled, “Customer Satisfaction of Banking Services: An Overview” has studied to assess the measurement criteria and to evaluate customer satisfaction regarding banking services and evaluate the level of satisfaction of customer services provided by the banks. He concluded that the bank has to keep in mind the mantra that “Customer is the King” and banks exist to serve them and should practice a range of services which fulfill customers’ satisfactions.

Nikhil Chandrashil & Bhagban Das, August (2008) conducted study on Customer Satisfaction with regard to Banking: An Application of QFD –Management Research, Vol.7, No.8. The study reveals that Customers nowadays are very choosy about the way they spend their money. Quality is the first and foremost preference. Therefore, it is of utmost importance for every organization to understand, respect, and satisfy their customer’s needs and feelings continuously.

Ashok Kumar and Rajesh (2009) found from the study that both public sector banks and private sector banks lack one or the other aspect of service quality and there is no significant difference between overall customer satisfactions in the banks, and concluded that banks should aim at satisfying the customers by providing maximum features in their banking services. Technological up gradation can be undertaken through implementation of core banking solutions and development of techno-savvy innovative products and services should be carried out.

Satendra Thakur (2011) examined the effect of service quality and customer satisfaction on customer loyalty among the group of customers in Indian banking industries. The results of the study indicated that customer satisfaction is significantly and positively related with customer loyalty and customer satisfaction is found to be an important mediator between service quality and customer loyalty. The author concluded that banking service providers should take right course of action to win customer satisfaction by providing better service quality in order to create loyal customer.

Ravi and Kundan basavaraj (2013) analyzed the customer preference and satisfaction towards banking services both private and public banks in Shivagangai district. The authors found business and vehicle loans are fast moving than other services and overall satisfaction resulted at 50%. Further, overall satisfaction on bank deposit schemes resulted positively while other services of banking still need to be given attention by focusing on customer issues. They authors suggested that, bankers should work towards 100% customer satisfaction that automatically fosters customer delight and to sustain customers on a long term basis.

3.Research Methodology

Sample for the study: Respondents for this study are the individuals who hold an active account with the randomly selected six branches of Kasaragodu district cooperative bank. The branches

selected are Kasaragodu main, Kanjangadu, Neeleswaram, Trikkarippur, Cheemeni and Chittarickkal.

Sample size: 120 respondents were chosen, twenty respondents each from the six branches

Type of sampling: Judgmental sampling, a type of non- probability sampling method has been used to select the respondents from the branches.

Type of research: The study fall under the category of descriptive research.

Data collection method: The researcher has approached the respondents by visiting them in the bank with a structured questionnaire and requested them to fill it up

Instrument used for data collection: The questionnaire developed and validated by P C Mandal S Bhattacharya, of Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, has used for data collection by slightly modifying the instrument.

Types of data used: Both primary and secondary data are used for this study. Primary data was collected with the help of a structured questionnaire directly from the respondents while secondary data was collected from the websites

Tools used for data analysis: Percentage analysis, weighted average, Kruskal Wallis Test and Mann-Whitney U methods are used for the data analysis

4.Objectives

- To understand the variable with the strongest association to the underlying latent construct
- To study whether there is a significant difference between the education of customers and their opinion on banking products and services
- To examine the difference between the gender of the customers and their opinion on banking products and services

5.Hypothesis

1. H0 : There is no statically significant difference between various levels of education of the respondents and their opinion on various attributes of customer satisfaction factors
2. H0 : There is no statically significant difference between the gender of the respondents and their opinion on various attributes of customer satisfaction factors
- 3.

6.Analysis and Findings

Table No. 1 Description of the sample

		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	81	67.5
	Female	39	32.5
	Total	120	100.0
Age	less than 20	2	1.7
	20 to 40	34	28.3
	40 to 60	44	36.7
	Above 60	40	33.3

	Total	120	100.0
Education	School	44	36.7
	Higher secondary	29	24.2
	Degree	39	32.5
	P G	7	5.8
	others	1	.8
	Total	120	100.0
Occupation	Govt employed	10	8.3
	Pvt. employed	20	16.7
	Self employed	30	25.0
	Professional	3	2.5
	House wife	25	20.8
	Retired	22	18.3
	Agriculture	7	5.8
	Others	3	2.5
Total	120	100.0	
Marital Status	Married	110	91.7
	Unmarried	10	8.3
	Total	120	100.0
Monthly Income	less than 10000	26	21.7
	10001 to 20000	58	48.3
	20001 to 40000	28	23.3
	40001 to 60000	7	5.8
	Above 60001	1	.8
	Total	120	100.0

Source: Primary data

The table given above gives a description of the sample taken for the study. We can see that majority of the respondents are male with just school education who are aged 40 years and above. Almost all of them are married and their monthly income was less than rupees twenty thousand a month.

Objective 1

Table No. 2: Weighted average score for various attributes of the factors of customer satisfaction

Sl.No.	Particulars	Weighted average score
	Factor1: Service Capabilities	
1	Availability of Computerized Banking System	486
2	Less waiting time for customers	491

3	Availability of Centralized Banking System	481
4	Standardized procedures followed for services provided by banks	486
	Factor2: Customer Services	
5	Availability of a prompt customer complaint mechanism	476
6	Availability of customer helpline phone numbers	428
7	Database for maintenance of updated customer information	429
	Factor3: ATM services	
8	Availability of ATM services round-the-clock	472
9	Fast replacement of ATM cards on expiry by banks	392
10	Universal accessibility of ATM cards at ATMs of other banks	396
	Factor4: Employees	
11	Proper attitude shown by the employees while serving customers.	440
12	Efficiency of the employees of banks.	494
13	Domain knowledge of the employees of banks.	516
	Factor5: Paperless Banking	
14	SMS alerts on mobiles provided by banks for different transactions	485
15	Debit card/credit card facilities at various outlets.	446
16	Availability of online banking services.	416
	Factor6: Service Quality	
17	Security of online transactions in ATMs.	460
18	Overall service quality provided by banks.	507
19	Prompt service provided by banks.	519
	Factor7: Product Features	
20	Low processing charges by banks for various types of loans.	413
21	Low money transfer charges by banks.	351
22	Low interest rates charged by banks for various types of loans.	293
23	Low installment amount charged by banks for loans	309
24	Less processing time for getting loans.	459

Source: Primary data

The above table shows that ; Less waiting time for customers, Availability of a prompt customer complaint mechanism, Availability of ATM services round-the-clock, Domain knowledge of the employees of banks, SMS alerts on mobiles provided by banks for different transactions, Prompt service provided by banks and Less processing time for getting loans have the strongest association with the respective factors such as Service Capabilities, Customer service, ATM Services, Employees, Paperless banking, Service quality and the product features.

Objective 2

Table No. 3 :Statistics^{a,b}

	Computerized	Waiting time	Core Banking	Procedures	Complaint Mechanism	Helpline
Chi-Square	.796	5.892	.421	2.429	1.961	2.780

df	3	3	3	3	3	3
Asymp. Sig.	.850	.117	.936	.488	.581	.427

a. Kruskal Wallis Test
 b. Grouping Variable: Education

Test Statistics^{a,b}

	Customer Database	Round the clock	Card replacement	Accessibility	Attitude	Efficiency
Chi-Square	.996	1.908	.348	.957	.616	8.850
df	3	3	3	3	3	3
Asymp. Sig.	.802	.592	.951	.812	.893	.031

a. Kruskal Wallis Test
 b. Grouping Variable: Education

Test Statistics^{a,b}

	Knowledge	SMS Alert	Card facilities	Online banking	Security	Quality
Chi-Square	3.927	1.106	.204	.648	2.973	4.427
df	3	3	3	3	3	3
Asymp. Sig.	.269	.776	.977	.885	.396	.219

a. Kruskal Wallis Test
 b. Grouping Variable: Education

Test Statistics^{a,b}

	Promptness	Processing charges	Transfer charges	Interest rates	Instalment amounts	Processing time
Chi-Square	6.963	2.626	4.811	2.247	2.263	6.396
df	3	3	3	3	3	3
Asymp. Sig.	.073	.453	.186	.523	.520	.094

a. Kruskal Wallis Test
 b. Grouping Variable: Education

The above tables show the variance among the respondents with different levels of educational qualification and their opinion on various attributes of the customer satisfaction factors. It is found that *employee efficiency* (p-value 0.031) is the only variable, so the null hypothesis rejected and we can conclude there is statistically significant variation among the respondent's levels of educational qualifications and their opinion on employee efficiency.

Objective 3

Table No.4: Test Statistics^a

	Computerized	Waiting time	Core Banking	Procedures	Complaint Mechanism	Helpline
Mann-Whitney U	1506.000	1423.500	1564.500	1383.500	1379.000	1568.000
Wilcoxon W	4827.000	4744.500	2344.500	4704.500	2159.000	4889.000
Z	-.680	-.963	-.099	-1.351	-1.542	-.072
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.496	.336	.921	.177	.123	.943

a. Grouping Variable: Gender
Test Statistics^a

	Customer Database	Round the clock	Card replacement	Accessibility	Attitude	Efficiency
Mann-Whitney U	1570.000	1438.000	1376.000	1471.500	1456.000	1556.500
Wilcoxon W	4891.000	4759.000	2156.000	2251.500	2236.000	4877.500
Z	-.060	-1.059	-1.663	-.752	-.906	-.140
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.952	.289	.096	.452	.365	.889

a. Grouping Variable: Gender
Test Statistics^a

	Knowledge	SMS Alert	Card facilities	Online banking	Security	Quality
Mann-Whitney U	1575.500	1353.000	1399.000	1514.000	1551.500	1414.500
Wilcoxon W	2355.500	2133.000	4720.000	2294.000	2331.500	4735.500
Z	-.025	-1.675	-1.293	-.393	-.198	-1.103
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.980	.094	.196	.695	.843	.270

a. Grouping Variable: Gender
Test Statistics^a

	Promptness	Processing charges	Transfer charges	Interest rates	Instalment amounts	Processing time
Mann-Whitney U	1481.500	1366.000	1493.000	1519.000	1551.500	1466.500

Wilcoxon W	4802.500	4687.000	4814.000	4840.000	4872.500	4787.500
Z	-.628	-1.328	-.516	-.404	-.176	-.910
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.530	.184	.606	.686	.861	.363

a. Grouping Variable: Gender

We can see from the above tables that, all the p- values are above 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and it can be concluded that there is no significant difference between the gender of the respondents and their opinion on various attributes of customer satisfaction factors.

7.Conclusion

The district cooperative banks in Kerala are grown-up to a higher level that now they offer the services and facilities that are as competent as the one offered by any other well established commercial bank. The present study has made an attempt to evaluate the opinion of the 120 sample customers towards the products, services and facilities offered by the selected six branches of the Kasaragodu district cooperative bank. The information was collected on factors such as Service capabilities, Customer services, ATM services, Employees, Paperless banking, Service quality and Product features. Statistical tools such as Kruskal Wallis Test and Mann-Whitney U, Weighted average and Percentage analysis, were used to analyze the data collected. It was found that here is statistically significant variation among the respondent’s levels of educational qualifications and their opinion on employee efficiency as the educated customers expect for higher efficiency. The study has also revealed that there is no significant difference between the gender of the respondents and their opinion on various attributes of customer satisfaction factors.

8.Limitations of the study and further scope of research:

Here the researcher has made an effort to study the customer’s opinion on various factors of customer satisfaction of Kasaragodu district cooperative bank by investigating a sample of one hundred and twenty respondents. The customers of the Kasaragodu district cooperative bank branches were the center of the study and therefore it suggests for like studies in other regions. The research was mainly on the data collected through the slightly modified instrument developed by Mandal PC, Bhattacharya S and the assessments of the responses confines to the items in that standard instrument. If a further modified version of the instrument is used, more pertinent information could be collected and hence more comprehensive studies could be conducted in future. Increased sample size and use of more of statistical tools for analyzes shall increase the accuracy and will furnish extra findings to the study.

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